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ENHANCING EDUCATIONAL OUTCOMES THROUGH MOBILE COMMUNICATION-BASED ON ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE TECHNOLOGIES

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ABSTRACT

The communication process in digital systems is still the background of the needs of communicators and communicants, especially in educational services. Therefore, the study explores the influence of mobile communication based on iOS technology in improving AI in the field of education among educators in Asia and Canada?; the influence of mobile communication based on Android technology in improving AI in the field of education among educators in Asia and Canada?; the influence of API technology in improving AI in the field of education among educators in Asia and Canada?; and the influence of communication based on iOS, Android and API technology together in improving AI in the field of education among educators in Asia and Canada?. The research method uses an Explanatory Survey to educators in Asia and Canada. The findings show that the role of mobile communication through iOS and Android technology is able to improve the ability of educators in mastering AI in the field of education in Asia and Canada; API technology has an effect on improving AI in the field of education among educators in Asia and Canada; together that mobile communication based on iOS, Android, and API technology together is able to improve the achievement of AI in the field of education in Asia and Canada. The findings of mobile communication research through iOS, Android, and API technology are determining factors in mastering AI in the field of education among educators in Asia and Canada and can be disseminated more widely.

KEYWORDS: Mobile Communication; IOS; Android; Education; Artificial Intelligence.

1. INTRODUCTION

Student motivation and engagement in elementary school are two key factors that determine the success of the A series of research projects focused on the ongoing development of the VCDLN-Learning, Database, and Mobile multiplatform systems has left a gap analysis in the digital communication aspect. Communication studies, particularly those based on Artificial Intelligence (AI), or innovations in the implementation of notification systems through API (Application Programming Interface) technology, require further research. Similarly, the application of mobile technology products, such as Android and iOS, is still assumed to contribute and warrant further investigation. Therefore, these three elements have been designated as specific variables, partially or simultaneously considered as homework in this research. This condition is assumed to be necessary for educators who have a long reach from their students and require adequate networking and digital learning communication systems, such as in Indonesia, Asia in general, and Canada with its vast territory.

Thus, the phenomenon of mobile digital communication skills by educators using mobile phones has become a fundamental requirement in the implementation of distance learning, especially when this distance learning utilizes AI technology products. Therefore, educators in several Asian countries and Canada need to be able to learn and master a number of AI applications that can assist them in preparing for teaching and even developing teaching materials.

Based on this analysis, several supporting studies, including the development of digital database systems and virtual learning access systems supported by productive learning communities, are predicted to become important innovations in the current digital era, such as AI. This is evidenced by Magma Learning in the European Union and Liquid Learning in the Asia Pacific region. With virtual learning innovations and AI support in education (Chu, Hwang, and Tu 2022), educators who use and produce digital learning resources will be supported and motivated. Research that has addressed virtual learning innovations, digital learning content developers, and database system development has been conducted by Darmawan et al. (2024).

The research questions in this study include: (1) What is the influence of iOS-based mobile communication technology on improving AI in education among educators in Asia and Canada? (2) How does Android technology-based mobile

communication influence AI in improving the field of education in the environment of educators in Asia and Canada?; How does API (Application Programming Interface) technology influence AI in improving the field of education in the environment of educators in Asia and Canada?; and (4) How does iOS, Android and API technology-based mobile communication influence together in improving AI in the field of education in the environment of educators in Asia and Canada?.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1. Mobile Communication

Mobile communication is the process of exchanging information between individuals or groups through mobile devices, such as smartphones, tablets, or laptops. Mobile communication theory discusses how mobile technology influences human communication behavior and how individuals interact with mobile technology. The main theory of mobile communication is the Uses and Gratifications Theory (Hajdarmataj and Paksoy 2023). This theory states that individuals use mobile technology to fulfill their needs and desires, such as the need for information, entertainment, or socialization. Furthermore, the Diffusion of Innovations Theory (Rogers and Everett 1983) explains how mobile technology is adopted and used by individuals and groups. From a community perspective, mobile communication is based on the Theory of Social Change (Coughenour and Applebaum 1972). This theory states that mobile technology enables individuals to connect with others and form social relationships wherever they are (Gültekin and Bayat 2014).

Therefore, the main concept of mobile communication is mobility, which refers to the ability of individuals to move and communicate through mobile devices (Alkhazaali et al. 2017). Next is Connectivity, namely an individual's ability to connect with other people and social networks through mobile devices. Finally, Interactivity, namely an individual's ability to interact with mobile devices and digital content.

On the other hand, mobile communication has changed the way individuals communicate and interact with technology. Mobile communication theory discusses how mobile technology influences human communication behavior and how individuals interact with mobile technology, as discussed in (McQuail and Mark Deuze 2020). However, mobile technology also has criticisms and challenges that need to be addressed to ensure its effective and responsible use, as examined by (Rodi

and Stevanovi 2015).

2.2. *Technology IOS*

IOS (Internet of Services) technology is a concept that allows devices and systems to communicate and interact over the internet. IOS enables integration between devices, systems, and applications to create more effective and efficient services, including in education (Devices and Enhance 2011). There are three theories that form the basis of IOS technology, namely Systems Theory, which states that IOS is a system consisting of components that interact to create services. Next is Network Theory, where this theory explains how IOS allows devices and systems to communicate and interact over the internet network, as done by Apple (Apple Industry 2011). Finally, Service Theory, which places IOS technology to enable the creation of more effective and efficient services through integration between devices, systems, and other applications such as with Android as developed for educational services (Apple Industry 2011; Cloud and Server 2019).

The main concepts of iOS technology are (1) Integration: iOS enables integration between devices, systems, and applications to create more effective and efficient services; (2) Interoperability: iOS enables devices and systems to communicate and interact through the same standards and protocols, and (3) Scalability: iOS enables the addition and reduction of resources to meet service needs. One of the interesting impacts of iOS technology in the field of AI Education is efficiency, iOS enables increased efficiency in business and operational processes, especially when collaborated with Android mobile phones (Cloud and Server 2019). Another positive impact is productivity where iOS enables increased productivity through integration between devices, systems, and applications by both admins and educators as users of educational services, especially distance education or in the classroom as explained by (Devices and Enhance 2011). In addition, it also has a positive impact on the quality of the system as a whole. So, improving service quality with iOS technology enables improving service quality through the creation of more effective and efficient services and requires a user guide (Inc. 2013).

Some applications of iOS technology include Smart Home, where iOS allows control and monitoring of homes and schools through mobile devices as an effort to build ecosystems with Android smartphones and Apple iOS (Brem and Tidd 2012). In the 2025 era, there is also a Smart City where iOS technology allows control and monitoring of cities through mobile devices. When AI starts to boom,

Industry 4.0 with the role of iOS allows control and monitoring of production processes through mobile devices, this is what is called the Value Chain (Peppard and Rylander 2006) which can be applied in educational services. Therefore, in this study, iOS technology is directed to support educators in mastering AI in the field of education. So, it can be emphasized that iOS technology is a concept that allows devices and systems to communicate and interact via the internet. iOS enables integration between devices, systems, and applications to create more effective and efficient services as researched by (Ma et al. 2019). However, iOS also has criticisms and challenges that need to be addressed to ensure that iOS technology is used effectively and responsibly.

2.3. *Android Technology*

Android technology is a mobile operating system developed by Google. Android enables mobile devices such as smartphones and tablets to run applications and perform various functions. In the context of this research, it is supported by the following main theories: First, Operating System Theory (uomus 2022): This theory states that Android is an operating system that manages mobile device resources and provides services to applications. Second, Application Theory which explains how Android applications are developed and run on mobile devices. Third, Network Theory: This theory states that Android enables mobile devices to communicate and interact over the internet. These three theories can be adopted in educational services, as researched by (Resuello 2017).

The main concept of Android technology is Open Source, where Android technology is an open-source operating system that allows developers to develop and modify learning source code (Agustina, Farida, and Irfan 2024; Hanafi 2012). Another contribution comes from the Linux Kernel: Android uses the Linux kernel as the basis for its operating system. Likewise, the concept of the Application Sandbox (Herrero Herranz et al. 2019) allows Android to enhance application security and privacy.

The positive impacts of Android technology have been widely felt, such as the increase in smartphone usage worldwide, which has boosted mobile application development. This research has also analyzed the increased connectivity, where Android has enhanced connectivity between mobile devices and the internet (Resuello 2017). Some examples of Android technology in the form of applications include social media applications like Facebook and Twitter (Bicen and Cavus 2012; Karamshuk et al. 2017; Morales-I-gras et al. 2021), gaming applications

like PUBG and Mobile Legends (Sweidan and Darabkh 2018), and even productivity applications like Microsoft Office and Google Docs (Bahtiar 2022) in offices. Thus, it can be affirmed that Android technology is a mobile operating system that enables mobile devices to run applications and perform various functions. Android has increased smartphone usage, application development, and connectivity worldwide, especially for Education services (Ma et al. 2019; Taufik et al. 2025).

2.4. Artificial Intelligence in Education

Artificial Intelligence (AI) is a technology that enables machines to perform tasks typically performed by humans, such as learning, reasoning, and decision-making (Krstić, Aleksić, and Krstić 2022). In education, AI can be used to improve the quality of learning and improve student learning outcomes as found in research (Cukurova, Luckin, and Kent 2020). In the context of education, there are a number of supporting theories, namely (a) Machine Learning Theory: This theory states that AI can be used to improve the quality of learning by using machine learning algorithms, one of which is in the application of MOOC (Pérez-Arteaga et al. 2025); (b) Artificial Intelligence Theory, this theory explains how AI can be used to improve student learning outcomes by using artificial intelligence techniques; and (3) Personalized Education Theory, which states that AI can be used to improve the quality of learning by providing personalized education for each student, as in the current application of Generative AI (Lo, Wong, and Chan 2025).

The scientific basis for this theory in the context of education includes Adaptive Learning, where AI can be used to improve the quality of learning by providing adaptive learning for each student. The need for Automated Assessment: Ideally, AI can be used to improve the quality of assessment by providing automated assessment for each student, as in the use of Generative AI (Gruenhagen et al. 2024). As Virtual Assistance, AI can be used to improve the quality of learning by providing virtual assistance for each student. An important foundation is also biocommunication (Darmawan 2012), which emphasizes that AI is based on the brain's automatic functioning system, starting from specific areas such as the prefrontal, frontal, temporal, parietal, occipital, and central nervous systems, which can be mimicked by AI systems.

In the context of this research, it is assumed that the impact of AI in education can determine improvements in learning quality. AI can be used to

improve learning quality by providing personalized and adaptive learning through mobile communication (Bajorath 2023). On the other hand, it is also assumed that it can support improved learning outcomes. AI can be used to improve student learning outcomes by providing automated assessments and virtual assistance (Rodrigues et al. 2024). Most importantly, for increased efficiency, AI can be used to improve efficiency in education by providing automated and personalized learning.

Some examples of AI applications in education include AI-based adaptive learning systems through Android mobile phones (Resuello 2017). AI can be used to develop adaptive learning systems that can improve learning quality. In automated learning assessment, AI can be used to develop automated assessment systems that can improve assessment quality. Virtual learning assistance, the application of AI, develops virtual assistance systems that can improve learning quality, but must still comply with ethical standards (Knight 2025). Finally, it can be emphasized that AI is a technology that can be used to improve learning quality and enhance student learning outcomes. AI can be used to provide personalized, adaptive, and automated learning. However, AI also has criticisms and challenges that need to be addressed to ensure that AI is used effectively and responsibly in education.

3. METHOD

This study used a quantitative approach with an explanatory survey method (Cresswell 2013) on a population of teachers who are members of the VCDLN-Learning community. The research was conducted in Uzbekistan, Indonesia, and Canada for 6 months. The number of samples taken purposively (Campbell et al. 2020) was 60 people from Uzbekistan, Indonesia, and Canada. Data analysis was conducted to test the proposed hypothesis using multiple regression (Allison 1999).

4. RESULT

4.1. The Influence of IOS Technology-Based Mobile Communication in Improving AI In the Educational Field Among Educators in Asia and Canada.

The research process was carried out through an explanatory survey using a questionnaire instrument to measure the influence of Variable X1, namely the Influence of IOS Technology-Based Mobile Communication on the improvement of AI in the field of Education among educators in Asia and Canada, carried out in the following stages.

Table 1: Regression Statistics.

<i>Regression Statistics</i>	
Multiple R	0,6242
R Square	0,3896
Adjusted R Square	0,3791
Standard Error	0,5545
Observations	60

From Table 1 above, it can be seen that the correlation value between iOS Technology-Based Mobile Communication and AI Achievement in Education among educators in Asia and Canada is positive at 0.6242 and is included in the High category. Meanwhile, the determination value of iOS Technology-Based Mobile Communication on AI Achievement in Education is obtained at 0.3896 or 38.96%. Thus, iOS Technology-Based Mobile Communication can explain the success of AI mastery in Education by educators in Asia and Canada by 38.96% and the rest is influenced by other factors and supports research from (Alkhazaali et al. 2017; Sweidan and Darabkh 2018). This finding

shows the importance of AI mastery in Education in the learning process, especially when educators must utilize online learning massively (Pérez-Arteaga et al. 2025). Likewise, mobile communication will help educators maintain ethical AI use when carrying out their duties (Knight 2025). Likewise, educators must re-understand what is meant by beneficial AI in education (Eyal 2025; Jeong 2025), and they also. Furthermore, to test the significance level of the influence of iOS-based mobile communication on AI achievements in education, as research by Alzahrani (2024) suggests, where educational services can be mobile (Jojo et al. n.d.) can be calculated in this research, as shown in Table 2.

Table 2: Coefficients.

	Coefficients	Standard Error	t Stat	P-value	Lower 95%	Upper 95%	Lower 95,0%	Upper 95,0%
Intercept	0,0876	0,6365	-0,1377	0,8910	-1,3618	1,1865	-1,3618	1,1865
Mobile Communication Based on iOS Technology (X1)	1,0013	0,1646	6,0846	0,0000	0,6719	1,3307	0,6719	1,3307

From Table 2 above, the regression equation can be formulated as $Y = 0.0876 + 1.0013X_1$. Therefore, the effect of X1, or iOS-Based Mobile Communication Technology, on the Improvement of AI in Education among educators in Asia and Canada is positive. Therefore, when the value of X1, or if the Communication Based on iOS Technology score increases by one point, the AI score in Education will increase by 1.0013. This finding aligns with research conducted by Gruenhagen et al. (2024). A key aspect

of this research is the impact of communication skills on enhancing success during evaluations (Kizilcec et al. 2024). Similarly, when educators must quickly assess students after they have completed learning, the skill of utilizing AI for assessment tasks is crucial (Al-Bogami and Alahmadi 2025; Schmidt et al. 2025). Furthermore, to test the significance of these regression coefficients and test the linearity of the regression line equation, an ANOVA test was used, as shown in Table 3.

Table 3: Tabel Anova.

ANOVA	Df	SS	MS	F	Significance F
Regression	1	11,3846	11,3846	37,0228	0,0000
Residual	58	17,8352	0,3075		
Total	59	29,2198			

From Table 3 above, it shows that the regression line equation and the level of linearity of the line are determined based on the F-calculation value, which is 37.0228 with a significance value of 0.0000, which means it is smaller than Alpha 0.05. So it can be explained that there is a significant influence of iOS-based Mobile Communication on the Improvement

of AI in the Educational Field in the Asian and Canadian Educator environment, this finding indirectly supports research from (Yu, Wang, and Zhang 2025; Zhang, Wu, and Chen 2024). So, the proposed Research Hypothesis (Hi) that "There is a Positive and significant influence between iOS-based Mobile Communication on AI Achievements in the

Educational Field in the Asian and Canadian educator environment", can be accepted. So, when teachers have to use AI products such as ChatGPT, they will be ready, this supports research from (Considerations and Analysis 2025). The Counter Hypothesis (Ho) is rejected, namely "There is no Positive and significant influence between iOS-based Mobile Communication on AI Achievements in the Educational Field in the Asian and Canadian educator environment".

4.2. The Influence of Android-Based Mobile Communication Technology in Improving AI In the Field of Education in the Asian and Canadian Educational Environment.

The research process was carried out through an explanatory survey using a questionnaire instrument to measure the influence of Variable X2, namely the Influence of Android Technology-Based Mobile Communication on the improvement of AI in the field of Education among educators in Asia and Canada, carried out in the following stages.

Table 4: Regression Statistics.

Regression Statistics	
Multiple R	0,4233
R Square	0,1792
Adjusted R Square	0,1650
Standard Error	0,6431
Observations	60

From table 4 above, it can be seen that the correlation value between Android-based Mobile Communication and AI Achievement in the Educational Sector among educators in Asia and Canada is positive at 0.4233 and is included in the Moderate category. This finding will strengthen research from (Resuello 2017). Meanwhile, the determination value of Android-based Mobile Communication on AI Achievement in the Educational Sector was obtained at 0.1792 or 17.92% which is quite supportive of research from

(Ekwonwune et al. 2022). Thus, Android-based Mobile Communication can explain the success of AI mastery in the Educational Sector by educators in Asia and Canada by 17.92% and the rest is influenced by other factors, but educators will not be anxious when they have to learn mobile communication as research from (Ekwonwune et al. 2022; Zhang et al. 2024). Based on these findings, educators will be able to apply their skills to detect viruses by communicating with their colleagues via their mobile phones (Keteku et al. 2024).

Table 5: Regression Coefficient.

	Coefficients	Standard Error	t Stat	P-value	Lower 95%	Upper 95%	Lower 95,0%	Upper 95,0%
Intercept	1,9866	0,5055	3,9302	0,0002	0,9748	2,9985	0,9748	2,9985
Android Technology-Based Mobile Communication (X2)	0,5317	0,1494	3,5582	0,0008	0,2326	0,8308	0,2326	0,8308

From Table 5 above, it shows that the coefficient can be formulated into a regression equation, namely $Y^{\wedge} = 1.9866 + 0.5317X_2$, thus the influence of X2, namely Android Technology-Based Mobile Communication on the Improvement of AI in the Education Sector in the Asian and Canadian educator environment is positive. Thus, when the value of X2 or Android Technology-Based Mobile Communication increases by one point, the value of AI in the Education Sector will increase by 0.5317. This finding is in line with research from (Resuello

2017; Yalçın and Yıldırım 2024). Furthermore, to test the level of significance of the regression coefficient formed and the linearity test of the regression line equation, the ANOVA test is used as can be seen in the following ANOVA table. This finding shows that Android technology in mobile phones (Yalçın and Yıldırım 2024) owned by educators will help them in their confidence to understand a number of message engineering practices they need, such as when asking questions on ChatGPT in class (Resuello 2017).

Table 6: Anova.

ANOVA	df	SS	MS	F	Significance F
Regression	1	5,2355	5,2355	12,6608	0,0008

Residual	58	23,9843	0,4135		
Total	59	29,2198			

From Table .6 above shows that the equation of the regression line and the level of linearity of the line can be seen from the F-calculated value of 12.6608 with a significance value of 0.0008 which means it is smaller than Alpha 0.005. So, it can be explained that there is a significant influence of Android Technology-based Mobile Communication on the Improvement of AI in the Field of Education in the Asian and Canadian Educator environment. So the proposed Research Hypothesis (Hi) that "There is a Positive and significant influence between Android Technology-based Mobile Communication on AI Achievements in the Field of Education in the Asian and Canadian educator environment", can be accepted., this finding prepares educators in utilizing Android for their students such as research from (Sweidan et al. 2017; Yalçın and Yıldırım 2024) and the counter Hypothesis (Ho) is rejected namely "There is no Positive and significant influence between Android Technology-based Mobile Communication on AI Achievements in the Field of

Education in the Asian and Canadian educator environment". Mastery of AI in the field of education is very important, especially when educators know that almost all of their students have Android cellphones (Lo et al. 2025), it will make it easier to understand the importance of AI when they communicate in class, whether it is more effective or vice versa (Ba et al. 2025; Lo et al. 2025).

4.3. The Impact of API (Application Programming Interface) Technology in Improving AI In Education in the Environment of Asian and Canadian Educators.

The research process was carried out through an explanatory survey using a questionnaire instrument to measure the influence of Variable X3, namely the influence of API technology on improving AI in the field of education among educators in Asia and Canada, carried out in the following stages.

Table 7: Regression Statistics.

Regression Statistics	
Multiple R	0,4071
R Square	0,1657
Adjusted R Square	0,1513
Standard Error	0,6483
Observations	60

From Table 7 above, it can be seen that the correlation value between API Technology and AI Achievement in Education among educators in Asia and Canada is positive at 0.4071 and is included in the Moderate category. This finding is positive and supports the work of an educator when retrieving educational data using their mobile phone from the database they access. Therefore, to obtain valid data, API technology is needed (Api et al. 2013; Merskin 2020). The determination value of API Technology on AI Achievement in Education is obtained at 0.1657 or 16.57%. Thus, Technology can explain the success of

AI mastery in Education by educators in Asia and Canada by 16.57%, with the rest influenced by other factors. This finding confirms that the influence of API technology is very important when educators have to convey original information through communication with the interface system of certain types of mobile learning applications, in line with the results of research conducted by (Chatzoglou and Kambourakis 2025; Pérez-Jorge et al. 2025). Likewise, when educators have to apply AI in certain learning, they must know and use their knowledge of API technology, as researched by (Tophel et al. 2025).

Table 8: Coefficients.

	Coefficients	Standard Error	t Stat	P-value	Lower 95%	Upper 95%	Lower 95,0%	Upper 95,0%
Intercept	0,9916	0,8202	1,2089	0,2316	-0,6502	2,6334	-0,6502	2,6334
Application Programming Interface (X3) Technology	0,6473	0,1907	3,3940	0,0012	0,2655	1,0290	0,2655	1,0290

Table 8 above shows that the regression line equation that can be formulated is $\hat{Y} = 0.9916 + 0.6473X_3$. Thus, the influence of X3, namely

Application Programming Interface (API) Technology, on the Improvement of AI in Education in the Asian and Canadian educational environment

is positive. So when the value of X3 or API Technology increases by one point, the AI value in Education will increase by 0.6000. This finding is in line with research on how to deliver material through AI-based learning websites that require the application of API Technology (Perron et al. 2025).

Furthermore, to test the level of significance of the formed regression coefficients and test the linearity of the regression line equation, the ANOVA test is used as can be seen in the following ANOVA table. 9, below.

Table 9: Anova.

ANOVA	<i>df</i>	<i>SS</i>	<i>MS</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>Significance F</i>
Regression	1	4,8416	4,8416	11,5191	0,0012
Residual	58	24,3782	0,4203		
Total	59	29,2198			

From Table 9 above, it shows that the regression line equation and the level of linearity of the line can be seen from the F-calculated value of 11.5191 with a significance value of 0.0012 which means it is smaller than Alpha 0.005. So, it can be explained that there is a significant influence of API Technology on the Improvement of AI in the Field of Education in the Asian and Canadian Educator environment, the results are positive. So the proposed Research Hypothesis (Hi) that "There is a Positive and significant influence between API Technology on AI Achievements in the Field of Education in the Asian and Canadian educator environment" can be accepted. and the counter Hypothesis (Ho) is rejected, namely "There is no Positive and significant influence between API Technology on AI Achievements in the Field of Education in the Asian and Canadian educator environment". This finding is in line with research from (Bellas et al. 2022; Carr 2022; Doroudi 2022; Vittorini, Menini, and Tonelli 2021).

4.4. The Influence of Mobile Communication Based on Ios, Android and API Technology Together in Improving AI In the Field of Education Among Educators in Asia and Canada.

The proposed Research Hypothesis (Ho) formulation is "There is a positive and significant influence between mobile communication based on IOS, Android, and API technology together on increasing the mastery of AI in the field of education by educators in Asia and Canada". To test the influence of the three variables together on this study `AI in Education in the environment of educators in Asia and Canada, an analysis of all regression coefficients or the influence of the three variables has been carried out. The results of the calculation can be formulated to form a multiple regression equation line like this, $Y^{\wedge} = 3.0742 + 1.0013X_1 + 0.5317X_2 + 0.6000X_3$ thus indicating that the influence is

positive and significant. Each variable positively provides an additional increase in points for a positive increase in Artificial Intelligence in Education. From these calculations, it can be concluded that H1 is accepted and Ho which states "There is no positive and significant influence between mobile communication based on IOS, Android, and API technology together on increasing the mastery of AI in the field of education by educators in Asia and Canada", is rejected. These findings indicate that educators' ability to master AI in educational applications is determined by their level of literacy in utilizing mobile communications on both Android and iOS devices (Eyal 2025; Knight 2025; Pérez-Arteaga et al. 2025). This finding, which demonstrates the support of iOS and Android mobile communications and API technology, has at least been supported by research (Ba et al. 2025; Orellana et al. 2025).

Predictions from both iOS and Android mobile technologies (Gültekin and Bayat 2014) adequately represent the need for learning communication tools and media for educators in Asia and Canada. Furthermore, when equipped with the API technology identified in this research, educators' need to master AI in educational applications will strengthen their role in rethinking the quality of AI obtained through mobile communications, as researched by Eyal (2025).

5. CONCLUSION

The results of this literature review confirm that the opening of learning (set induction) plays a strategic role From the results of the research and discussion of the problems in this study, it shows that the influence of the variable Mobile Communication based on IOS Technology is positive and significant by providing added value for educators from Asia and Canada in mastering AI in the field of Education positively and providing a high category influence. The influence of Mobile Technology based on

Android Technology provides a moderate category influence on the achievement of AI in the field of Education in the educational environment of Asia and Canada. From the third finding, especially the application of API Technology shows a positive influence and contribution with a moderate category and is able to predict the increase in AI in the field of Education in the educational environment of Asia

and Canada through its linear regression equation line. The joint influence between Mobile Communication based on IOS and Android Technology and the role of API Technology based on multiple regression analysis obtained positive results with a prediction of an increase in AI Achievement in the field of Education of educators in the high environment of Asia and Canada simultaneously.

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